

Original Research Report

Nutrient Analysis of Two Lesser-Known Indigenous Vegetables (Cocoyam and Sweet Potato Leaves) in Melon Soups

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Abstract: The study investigated the nutrient composition of two lesser-known indigenous vegetables (cocoyam and sweet potato leaves) in melon soups. The study was conducted to identify proximate composition in three types of melon soups. The instrument adopted for the study was laboratory analysis of food nutrients by four food Technologists using official methods of Association of Official Analytical Chemists. The data for food nutrients were collected in triplicate from the melon soups in the food analysis laboratory, raw triplicate values of each food nutrients in the soups were collected and analyzed using $\bar{X} \pm SD$ and ANOVA statistics to test the hypotheses 1 – 2. The findings revealed that cocoyam and sweet potato leaves melon soups are as rich as fluted pumpkin leaf melon soup in proximate nutrients, such as protein in cocoyam and sweet potato leaves had (9.81: 8.90 while fluted pumpkin had 9.58), moisture (65.02: 64.74 while fluted pumpkin had 65.17); fats (7.75: 10.65 while fluted pumpkin 10.45), carbohydrate (12.68: 8.30 fluted pumpkin 7.87), fibre (3.78: 7.19 while fluted pumpkin had 5.49), and ash (0.95: 0.95 and fluted pumpkin 1.44). The study showed that there were significant differences between the mean values of the nutrients in the proximate analysis. Therefore, the consumption of cocoyam and sweet potato leaves should be encouraged by all families in the country. Cocoyam and sweet potato leaves should be sold in the open markets same way the popular vegetables are sold such as fluted pumpkin (Ugu) leaf.

Keywords: Cocoyam, Lesser-Known, Soup, Sweet Potato, Vegetables

1. Introduction

Vegetable is the edible part of a plant that is consumed by humans as food and part of a savory meal. The leafy part of the vegetable plant is that part, which contain no seeds from culinary context. These vegetables are the leaves or stems of herbaceous plants, although flower calyces are also consumed as vegetables (Adenipekun et al., 2010). Similarly, Otitoju et al. (2014) and Okon et al. (2015) defined leafy vegetables as the fleshy and edible portion of herbaceous plants, which can be eaten raw and cooked with other condiments as soup. Leafy green vegetables play an important role in human nutrition, being mostly low in fat and carbohydrates (Yakubu et al, 2012). Leafy green vegetables are inexpensive, easily and quickly cooked and are rich in several nutrients such as vitamins, minerals, dietary fiber, proteins of higher biological value than some major staples for optimal functioning of the human body system (Elemo, et al., 2013). Otitoju et al. (2014) further observed leafy vegetables as those succulent plants grown mainly in farms and around homes, though some are wild in the forest. The wild leafy vegetables are rich in nutrients and natural sources of therapeutic agents, but they are lesser-known (unpopular or not well known). Lesser-known vegetables are edible vegetables neglected, underused, underutilized, traditional alternative and more lately referred to as forgotten vegetables. Lesser-known vegetables (neglected or underutilized plants) are those that could be and, in many cases, historically have been used for food and other uses on a larger scale (Oloyede et al, 2011). Cocoyam and Sweet potato leaves are known to be addressed as lesser known because the tubers are well known and used, as food, but the leaves are not used as such by people most especially in Nigeria.

Cocoyam is nutritionally superior to other roots and tubers are ranked third in importance after cassava and yam among the roots and tuber crops cultivated and consumed in Nigeria (Ogukwe et al., 2017). The cocoyam species in Nigeria are herbaceous monocotyledon tuberous plants from the family of Araceae and the edible members of Araceae family include xanthosoma species and the colocasiae species (Damilola, et al., 2013). According to Ogukwe et al. (2017) explained that, taro (*colocasia esculenta*) is known as ‘old cocoyam’ and malanga (*xanthosoma spp*) is ‘new cocoyam’. These two varieties are grown primarily for their edible roots although all parts of the plant are edible. Obidiegwu et al.(2016) opined that, cocoyam is an important food crop for more than four hundred million people worldwide, especially in the tropics and sub-tropics. The authors further explained that cocoyam represents an excellent source of carbohydrate, the majority being starch of which 17% - 28% is amylase and the remainder is amylopectin and the cocoyam starch is one of the most nutritious and 98.8% digestible, a quality attributed to its granule size making it ideal for people with digestive difficulties. Agbor et al. (2009) opined that, the leaves of cocoyam (*colocasia esculenta* var. *antiquorum*) contained significant amount of nutrients such as high crude lipid, crude protein and crude fiber. Ukpong et al. (2014) stated that, the leaves are cooked and eaten as vegetable, likewise in some parts of the south-south and south-east. However, Awak et al. (2017) opined that, cocoyam has a nutritional value comparable to sweet potato.

Sweet potatoes are tuberous crops with the botanical name *Ipomoea Batatas L.* According to Rudrappa (2009), *Ipomoea batatas* as a starch-rich tuber plant belongs to the bindweed or morning glory family of Convolvulaceae in the order of *Solanles*. “*Ipomoea*” direct translation resembles bindweed; the botanical name was derived from the greek words

ipos, meaning “bind weed” and “homoios”, meaning “resembling”, which is combined to form “Ipomoea”. However, Cole, (2011) stated that *Ipomoea batatas* is an herbaceous vine that has purplish medium sized flowers and large nutritious tuberous roots. According to Islam (2014) sweet potato is the sixth most important food crop in the world and it is important for the growing populations in Asian and African countries. The plant is a creeper with heart – shaped or lobed leaves with tapering ends and has smooth outer skin and the colour of the tubers ranges from purple, red, brown, pale yellow or white, depending on the variety, soil types, climate and available minerals (Cook, 2017; Rudrappa, 2009). According to Slam and Jalaluddin (2004), Sweet potato roots and tops possess a variety of chemical compounds relevant to human health. Sweet Potatoes is listed as one of the vegetables consumed by all ethnic groups in Ghana and some other African countries, though, only the tubers are consumed in large quantities especially in Nigeria (Ibok & Deborah, 2008). Similarly, Johnson and Pace (2010) observed that sweet potato leaves are consumed primarily in the islands of the Pacific Ocean and in Asian and some Africa countries, with limited consumption occurring in the United States. Aregheore (2012) also opined that sweet potato leaves are highly digestible, fairly rich in protein, a dietary source of fiber and essential fatty acids and free from toxins. Sweet Potato leaf contains protein and crude fiber, which is important for addressing deficiency diseases and colon disease when consumed in sauces or soups.

Soup is primarily a liquid food, generally served warm or hot (but may be served cool or cold), which is made by combining ingredients such as meat or fish and vegetables with stock, water or another liquid and other ingredients such as thickeners which are also condiments (melon, ogbono, achi, cocoyam, & tomatos). According to Fulton (2006) soup is a liquid food made by boiling or simmering meat, fish or vegetables with various added ingredients. Similarly, Goltz (2016) opined that, there are two main groups or variations of soups (clear soup and thick soup). The clear soups are bouillon and consommé (soup made from richly flavoured stock or bouillon that has been clarified, a process that uses egg whites to remove fat and sediments from stock), while the thick soups are classified depending upon the types of thickening agents used, which may include ogbono, melon, okra, cocoyam, yam, among others.

The use of melon in soup thickening is popular in almost every tribe or culture in Nigeria and Africa. Melon is popularly known as “egusi”; which is mostly grown for consumption by Africans to complement starchy foods such as fufu, eba, akpu, pounded yam among others (Okpala, 2016). The melon plant looks much like watermelon plant. However, on the inside of the melon fruit is white, dry and bitter pulp enough to be repulsive, while watermelon is red, luscious and sweet pulp. The melon (egusi) seed, according to Okpala (2016) is known as *colocynthis citrullus* (*cucurbita citrullus L.* or *citrullus Lanatus thumb*) and belong to the family of cucurbitaceae. It is known by various names such as bitter cucumber, pumpkin seeds, egusi melon, and vine of Sodom plant. Okpala (2016) and Ezekiel, et al. (2018) stated that, melon is a major soup ingredient and a common component of daily meals. The authors further observed that, melon is very high in nutritional value such as protein and fats such as Palmitic, Stearic, Linoleic, Oleic acids and very little amount of carbohydrate and calcium.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Research has it that, cocoyam and sweet potato leaves are rich in carbohydrates, proteins, fats, fiber, and moisture. Due to lack of awareness of their nutrient potentials, and economic advantage cocoyam and sweet potato leaves may bring to households, most people of the South East do not consume the leaves rather they plant and wait for the storage tubers to mature, harvest the tubers and give out the leaves to animals for feed with very few farmers consuming the harvested leaves. The leaves of cocoyam and sweet potato are being wasted or given to animals when they can be very useful source of vegetables to human. Secondly, during dry season, the very popular vegetables such as fluted pumpkin may not be easily available and expensive, these alternative (cocoyam and sweet potato leaves) may help ameliorate the scarcity of vegetables. Hence, the study was designed to ascertain the nutrient composition of these vegetables in melon soups. The Findings of this study would be of immense benefit to humanity, most especially; parents, homemakers, Home Economics teachers, nutritionists, dietitians, community health workers and the entire populace of the nation as this will provide them with information on the nutrients of the vegetables.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the nutrient composition of cocoyam and sweet potato leaves in melon soups in South East geopolitical zone. Specifically, the study sought to:

- (a) Determine the nutrient composition (proximate analysis) of cocoyam leaf soup.
- (b) Determine the nutrient composition (proximate analysis) of sweet potato leaf soup.

1.3. Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- (a) What are the nutrients (proximate) composition of cocoyam leaf soup and the popular fluted pumpkin vegetable soup (control)?
- (b) What are the nutrients (proximate) composition of sweet potato leaf soup and the popular fluted pumpkin vegetable soup (control)?

1.4. Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study and were tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance:

Ho₁: There was no significant difference in nutrients (proximate) composition between cocoyam leaf soup and the popularly used vegetables such as Fluted Pumpkin (Ugu leaf) soup

Ho₂: There was no significant difference in nutrient (proximate) composition between sweet potato leaf soup and the popularly used vegetables such as Fluted Pumpkin (Ugu leaf) soup.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The study was conducted using Experimental research design, which involves laboratory- based studies. This Laboratory-Based In-vitro Studies enabled the researcher to

examine the presence of specific variables (such as nutrients in the selected vegetables) using reagents under controlled environment.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The research was carried out with informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality of the respondents who voluntarily participated in the sensory evaluation of the study. The standard methods for sensory evaluation studies were strictly adhered to. The ethical demands of sensory evaluation as required in research studies were strictly complied with.

2.2. Area of the Study

The study was conducted in the South East, geopolitical zone of Nigeria. However, the vegetables for the study were collected from the farms of some indigenes of Nsukka and were identified in the department of crop science, faculty of Agriculture, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The study was conducted in the Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education Faculty of Vocational and Technical Education, University of Nigeria. The proximate analysis was conducted in the Department of Home Science and Nutrition Food Analysis Laboratory University of Nigeria Nsukka.

2.3. Population for the Study

There was no population for the study other than four foods Laboratory Technologist (research assistants) in the Department of Nutrition and Dietetics of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka who assisted the researcher in the determination of nutrients composition of the lesser-known vegetables soups (cocoyam and sweet potato).

2.4. Instruments for Data Collection

The standard instrument for nutrient analyses developed by Analysis of Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 2010) was used.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

The researchers with the help of four food Laboratory Technologists determined the proximate composition of the lesser-known vegetables (cocoyam (*colocasiae esculenta*'s) and sweet potato (*ipomoea batatas L.*'s) leaves) in melon soup in southeast zone using the method of Analysis of Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 2010) which is a standard instrument for chemical analysis for research questions 1-2.

2.6. Experimental Procedure for Food Nutrient Determination (materials and methods) For the Proximate Analysis

This involved the laboratory analytical process of determining the proximate composition (laboratory based in-vitro studies) which involves moisture, protein, fat, carbohydrate, ash and crude fibre determination. The samples of the lesser-known vegetables (*ipomoea batatas L.* and *colocasiae esculenta* leaves) in addition to the fluted pumpkin leaf (control) were bought from farmers within the University of Nigeria Nsukka. The fresh vegetables were washed, plucked, and shredded, made into melon soups.

2.7. Materials and Method of Soup Samples

- 3 milk cups of ground melon seeds (egusi)
- 2 cooking spoons of ground crayfish
- 300 ml or 2 milk cups of palm oil
- 1 big onion chopped
- Pepper to taste
- 1 litre of water

150g of Ugu leaf (fluted pumpkin)

150g of Cocoyam leaf

150g of Sweet potato leaf

Salt to taste

2.8. Method of Cooking

- (a) Place palm oil into a sauce pot and place over moderate heat for 2 minutes
- (b) Add the chopped onion to the hot oil and allow heating for 3minutes without burning
- (c) Add the grind melon to the hot onion oil and continue frying until melon forms lumps.
- (d) Add water to the fried melon and add pepper and stir the mixture in the saucepot and allow to boil for 10 minutes
- (e) Add the crayfish and salt, continue boiling for 5minutes.
- (f) Bring down the saucepot and share soup into three equal portions.
- (g) To the first portion add shredded sweet potato leaf and bring to boil for 2 minutes over high heat. (a short time was used to cook the vegetables because the soups will still be autoclaved at 60°c for about 6 hours).
- (h) To the second portion add the shredded cocoyam leaf and bring to boil for 2 minutes over high heat.
- (i) To the third portion, add the shredded fluted pumpkin leaf and bring to boil for 2 minutes.
- (j) The three melon soup samples were taken to the laboratory for proximate analysis.

The soup samples were dried at 60°c for six hours, ground to powder and were used for the analysis of the nutrients (moisture, protein, fat, carbohydrate, ash and crude fiber determination).

2.9. Data Analysis Technique

Research questions 1 and 2 were analyzed using standard formula for nutrients determination is expressed as percentage and mean \pm SD. The Hypotheses 1 – 2 was analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. The decision rule for the hypotheses stood at, any item less than 0.05 indicates no significant, and greater than 0.05 implied significant difference.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Research question one: What are the nutrients (proximate) composition of cocoyam leaf and fluted pumpkin leaf melon soups?

Table 1: Percentage, Mean and Standard deviation of the proximate analysis of cocoyam and fluted pumpkin leaves melon soups (mg/100g)

Nutrient parameters	Cocoyam leaf	Cocoyam leaf	Fluted pumpkin	Fluted pumpkin leaf
	Mean in %	$\bar{x} \pm SD$	leaf	$\bar{x} \pm SD$
			Mean in %	
Protein	9.81	9.81 \pm 0.03	8.58	9.58 \pm 0.10
Ash	0.95	0.95 \pm 0.01	1.44	1.44 \pm 0.02
Fats	7.75	7.75 \pm 0.47	10.45	10.45 \pm 0.32
Fiber	3.78	3.78 \pm 0.21	5.49	5.49 \pm 0.04
Moisture	65.02	65.02 \pm 0.36	65.17	65.17 \pm 0.50

Carbohydrate	12.68	12.68 ± 0.38	7.87	7.87 ± 0.64
Total	100		100	

Data represent means of triplicate determinations = mean, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 1 showed that, the $\bar{x} \pm SD$ rating of the proximate nutrients of the two vegetables used cocoyam leaf and fluted pumpkin leaf, which is the control. The result showed that; the $\bar{x} \pm SD$ protein content of cocoyam leaf (9.81 ± 0.03) is slightly higher than the fluted pumpkin leaf soup (9.58 ± 0.10). In the case of Ash, cocoyam leaf had lower $\bar{x} \pm SD$ content (0.95 ± 0.01) as compared to fluted pumpkin leaf (1.44 ± 0.02). The fat content of cocoyam leaf content (7.75 ± 0.47) was also lower than fluted pumpkin leaf soup (10.45 ± 0.02). The fiber $\bar{x} \pm SD$ content of cocoyam leaf (3.78 ± 0.21) was also lower than the fluted pumpkin leaf (5.49 ± 0.04). The moisture content of both vegetables was slightly close, ranging from 65.17 ± 0.50 to 65.02 ± 0.36 . While the carbohydrate content of cocoyam leaf (12.68 ± 0.38) was much higher than fluted pumpkin leaf (7.87 ± 0.64). However, cocoyam leaf melon soup was also nutritionally rich in proximate nutrients protein, fats, fiber, carbohydrate, moisture and ash.

3.2. Hypothesis one (H_{01}): There was no significant difference in proximate composition between Cocoyam leaf melon soup and the popularly used vegetables such as Fluted Pumpkin (Ugu leaf) melon soup.

Table 2: Analysis of Variance of proximate composition of cocoyam and fluted pumpkin leaves melon soups

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Protein	Between Groups	.001	2	.001	23.202.	.001
	Within Groups	.000	0	.		.
	Total	.001	2			
Ash	Between Groups	.000	2	.000	1.237.	.000
	Within Groups	.000	0	.		.
	Total	.000	2			
Fats	Between Groups	.445	2	.222	.908.	.000
	Within Groups	.000	0	.		.
	Total	.445	2			
Fibre	Between Groups	.085	2	.043	9.231.	.000
	Within Groups	.000	0	.		.
	Total	.085	2			
Carbohy	Between Groups	.289	2	.144	.960.	.009
	Within Groups	.000	0	.		.
	Total	.289	2			
Moisture	Between Groups	.262	2	.131	9.091.	.005
	Within Groups	.000	0	.		.
	Total	.262	2			

The mean difference is Significant at the $p \leq 0.05$ level

Table 2 showed that, there were significant differences in the mean proximate values of cocoyam leaf melon soup and fluted pumpkin leaf melon soup such as Protein ($F = 23.202$,

$p < 0.05$); ash ($F = 1.237$, $p < 0.05$); moisture ($F = 9.091$, $p < 0.05$); carbohydrate ($F = .960$, $p < 0.05$); fat ($F = .908$, $p < 0.05$) and fiber ($F = 9.231$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the research hypothesis was rejected.

3.3. *Research question two*: What are the nutrients (proximate) compositions of sweet potato leaf and fluted pumpkin leaf melon soup?

Table 3: Percentage, Mean and Standard deviation of the proximate analysis of Sweet Potato and fluted pumpkin leaves melon soup (mg/100g)

Nutrient parameters	Sweet Potato leaf Mean in %	Sweet Potato leaf $\bar{x} \pm SD$	Fluted pumpkin leaf Mean in %	Fluted pumpkin leaf $\bar{x} \pm SD$
Protein	8.90	8.90 ± 0.05	9.58	9.58 ± 0.10
Ash	0.95	0.95 ± 0.01	1.44	1.44 ± 0.02
Fats	10.65	10.65 ± 0.42	10.45	10.45 ± 0.32
Fibre	7.19	7.19 ± 0.99	5.49	5.49 ± 0.04
Moisture	64.74	64.74 ± 0.70	65.17	65.17 ± 0.50
Carbohydrate	8.30	8.30 ± 1.27	7.87	7.87 ± 0.64
Total	100		100	

Data represent means of triplicate determinations \bar{x} = means, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 3 showed the $\bar{x} \pm SD$ rating of the proximate analysis in the two vegetables used for the experiment (Sweet potato and fluted pumpkin leaves). The data above showed that sweet potato leaf had high nutrient composition as much as fluted pumpkin leaf. The protein content of fluted pumpkin is 9.58 ± 0.10 and sweet potato leaf had 8.90 ± 0.05 . The table also showed that the Ash content of the sweet potato leaf (0.95 ± 0.01) was lower when compared to fluted pumpkin leaf (1.44 ± 0.02). The table further showed that, fats content of sweet potato leaf was a little higher (10.65 ± 0.42) than the control (10.45 ± 0.32) - Ugu leaf. The fibre content of sweet potato leaf was higher with (7.19 ± 0.99) than the control (5.49 ± 0.04). The moisture content of fluted pumpkin leaf and sweet potato leaf were ranging from 65.17 ± 0.50 to 64.74 ± 0.70 . However, sweet potato leaf was a little lower than the fluted pumpkin leaf. The sweet potato leaf (8.30 ± 1.27) had higher carbohydrate content than the fluted pumpkin leaf (7.87 ± 0.64). The table showed that sweet potato leaf was higher in fats, fibre and carbohydrate while fluted pumpkin was higher in protein, ash and moisture.

3.4. *Hypothesis two (H₀₂)*: There was no significant difference in proximate composition between Sweet Potato leaf melon soup and the popularly used vegetables such as Fluted Pumpkin (Ugu leaf) melon soup

Table 4: Analysis of Variance test of proximate composition of sweet potato leaf and fluted pumpkin leaf melon soups

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Protein	Between Groups	.006	2	.003	321.	.000
	Within Groups	.000	0	.		
	Total	.006	2			
Ash	Between Groups	.000	2	.000	110	.000

	Within Groups	.000	0	.		
	Total	.000	2			
	Between Groups	.352	2	.176	101.	.001
Fats	Within Groups	.000	0	.		
	Total	.352	2			
	Between Groups	1.962	2	.981	987	.007.
Fibre	Within Groups	.000	0	.		
	Total	1.962	2			
	Between Groups	3.222	2	1.611	1.675	.000.
Carbohy	Within Groups	.000	0	.		
	Total	3.222	2			
	Between Groups	.967	2	.484	23.455	.000
Moisture	Within Groups	.000	0	.		
	Total	.967	2			

The mean difference is Significant at the $p \leq 0.05$ level

The hypothesis in table 4 showed that, there were significant difference in protein ($F= 321$, $p < 0.05$) fats ($F= 101$, $p < 0.05$); ash ($F= 110$, $p < 0.05$); carbohydrate ($F= 1.675$, $p < 0.05$); moisture ($F= 23.455$, $p < 0.05$) and fibre ($F= 987$, $p < 0.05$) of sweet potato leaf and fluted pumpkin leaf in melon soup. On this premise, the hypothesis was rejected.

The study found out that cocoyam leaf melon soup was rich in nutrients (protein, ash, fats, fiber, moisture and carbohydrates) like the popularly used vegetables (fluted pumpkin leaf). The study showed that cocoyam leaf melon soup had higher protein and carbohydrate than the fluted pumpkin leaf melon (control) soup, while the fluted pumpkin leaf melon soup had higher ash, fats, fiber and moisture. However, the mean values of both soup nutrients are within close range but the hypothesis tested showed that, there were significant differences at p-value of 0.05 which led to the rejection of the hypothesis. This showed that the vegetable is good in preventing constipation and protein energy malnutrition in both adult and children. The findings are in agreement with the submission of Kwenin, Wolli, and Dzomeku (2011) study on the nutrient composition of cocoyam leaf, which stated that cocoyam leaves are highly nutritive in protein, fiber, ash, carbohydrates and moisture. The study on cocoyam leaf observed that cocoyam leaf had appreciable quantity of protein, carbohydrates, fats, fiber, ash and moisture, which can be considered to be used as food. The findings of the proximate composition are in alliance with the submission of Ismail (2014) that, the leaves of cocoyam are very good sources of vitamin A, C and protein. The findings were also in consonance with Obidiegwu et al. (2016) which stated that cocoyam leaves contain significant levels of protein. Likewise, Tabiri et al. (2016) observed that melon seeds are high in protein, fiber, ash, and carbohydrate.

The study found out that sweet potato leaf melon soup was rich in nutrients, which include; protein, ash, fats, fiber, moisture and carbohydrate like the commonly used fluted pumpkin (Ugu) leaf. The study showed that some nutrients such as fats, fiber and carbohydrate in sweet potato leaf melon soup had higher mean values than fluted pumpkin leaf soup. Although, the fluted pumpkin melon soup had higher mean values in ash, protein and moisture than sweet potato leaf melon soup. Due to the mean differences, the hypothesis tested showed that, there were significant differences at p-value of 0.05, which led to

rejection of the hypothesis. However, the nutrients mean values of both soups are within range. The result of the findings on the proximate analysis concerning sweet potato leaf soup was in consonance with the submission of Thomas and Oyediran (2008) and Abubakar et al. (2010) studies, which stated that sweet potato leaf soups or dishes are rich in protein, fats, fiber, moisture, ash and carbohydrates. In similar way, Aregheore (2012) also stated that sweet potato leaves contain protein and crude fiber which are important for addressing deficiency diseases and colon diseases. These vegetables are good at promotion of bowel movement, anti-inflammation and antimicrobial activity due to the presence of good dietary fiber. Therefore, cocoyam and sweet potato leaves are good for the prevention of constipation and protein energy malnutrition in both children and adults.

4. Conclusion

Based on the study conducted, cocoyam and sweet potato leaves are highly nutritious as fluted pumpkins leaves in protein, carbohydrates, fiber, fats, ash and moisture. The cocoyam and sweet potato leaves could actually serve as alternative to the popularly utilized vegetables because these lesser-known vegetables can be used in preparing soups as demonstrated in the study. The consumption of cocoyam and sweet potato leaves should be encouraged by all families because these vegetables could help in the prevention of constipation and protein energy malnutrition in both children and adults. Home Economics Education should be encouraged financially by the federal and state government to conduct extension service in nutrition education. This is to enable populace in the rural areas to have access to good nutrition especially from crops or vegetables of these kinds. The production of cocoyam and sweet potato leaves should be encouraged by both the federal and state government. Cocoyam especially that had issues of production in the past in some localities should be encouraged to be grown at all cultural zone of the country through irrigation farming. Home Economists, Nutritionists and Dieticians should be sponsored by the federal and state government to create awareness in the consumption and utilization of cocoyam and sweet potato leaves in the nation by organizing seminars and workshops. The local traders should be encouraged to commercialize these vegetables in the markets just the same way the popular vegetables are sold in the open markets.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the Department of Home Economics Education, School of Vocational Education, Federal College of Education (Tech), Potiskum, Yobe State, Nigeria, and the laboratory assistants and data analysts for their assistance.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Priscilla B. Mberekpe designed the work and wrote the article. Chinyere A. Igbo proofread the article, and collected samples used for the research. Both authors participated in carrying out analysis of the samples. Both authors approved the final draft for publication.

Data Availability Statement

Original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Funding Information

The authors have no funding to disclose

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Publisher: Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka 41001, Nigeria

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